

Body Care as an Effort to Improve Beauty and Health for Post Partum Mothers in Lamongan Regency, East Java, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Pregnancy, childbirth and breastfeeding are natural and physiological processes for every woman who plays the role of a mother. The end of this quite long process is the birth of a baby which the parents have been waiting for. After the baby is born with the placenta, it will be the peak of adaptation for a mother and her baby. The mother will enter the postpartum and breastfeeding period where the mother will assume her new role. Some of these discomforts will bother the mother and cause increased morbidity in the mother. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that health care during the postpartum period can be started 24 hours after giving birth or when the mother is in a physiological postpartum state. This treatment can be carried out by competent personnel such as doctors, midwives or nurses. This health care is an effort to improve the level of health as a mother in general and during the postpartum period and breastfeeding in particular. From this adaptation process you will find some discomfort. This can be overcome with postpartum care. The research method used is descriptive quantitative. Using the total population, from the cross tabulation results, 65.7% of postpartum mothers who underwent postpartum care were in a healthy condition during the postpartum period (42 days). These results show that there is a tendency for mothers who undergo postpartum care to have a healthy body condition. From this, it becomes a reference that postpartum care is very important for postpartum mothers to be able to improve the mother's health status during the postpartum period and beyond

INTRODUCTION

The process of pregnancy, childbirth and postpartum are important parts for a woman. During this period, care is needed that is appropriate to each condition. Some of this care is mandatory and some is additional so that a mother is able to live through this period healthily and comfortably. Care and monitoring during this period is known as Ante Natal Care (ANC), Intra Natal Care (INC) and Post Natal Care (PNC). Government programs have touched on many things and are implemented in every period of pregnancy up to postpartum and breastfeeding. In addition to treatment with mandatory programs that have been established by the government, mothers during pregnancy, childbirth and postpartum are highly recommended to care for maternal health with several complementary therapies that have been researched and proven to be safe. A mother will adapt to these times. Mothers will experience both physical and psychological changes, including discomfort that arises from each phase.

Pregnancy, childbirth and breastfeeding are natural and physiological processes for every woman who plays the role of a mother. The end of this quite long process is the birth of a baby which the parents have been waiting for. After the baby is born with the placenta, it will be the peak of adaptation for a mother and her baby. The mother will enter the postpartum and breastfeeding period where the mother will assume her new role. From the adaptation process, several discomforts and health problems will be found that are usually felt by postpartum mothers, such as pain after giving birth, breast milk retention (ASI), postpartum bleeding, smelly discharge from the birth canal, swelling in the facial area, higher fever. from 2 days, swollen breasts, increased spots on the face, unkempt skin and psychological disorders in the form of baby blues and post partum depression. According to an article in an obstetrician consultation application, complaints that postpartum mothers often experience apart from bleeding include stretch marks appearing on the surface of the skin, changes in body shape and hair loss.'

From a preliminary study conducted on 10 postpartum mothers 1-7 days post partum, it was found that 8 mothers experienced postpartum complaints, 2 people did not experience complaints. These complaints included pain in the birth canal for 2 people, a dull face for 2 people, swollen breasts due to breast milk dams for 2 people, the mother had no appetite and often felt sad for 1 person, the mother couldn't rest comfortably for 1 person. Complaints that cannot be resolved properly will disrupt the postpartum and breastfeeding process. The mother will not be able to carry out her role optimally, the mother will feel unwell so her confidence in caring for the baby will also decrease, breast milk will not come out optimally so the baby will also lack nutrition. Such conditions will make it easier for mothers to get sick and experience psychological disorders. According to Yunita (2023), postpartum mothers must have "me time" with various positive activities regularly during pregnancy or after giving birth. "Me time" means deep breathing exercises, listening to favorite songs, listening to murotal for Muslim women or just beautifying yourself at the salon. This is done to prevent psychological discomfort which has a huge impact on the mother's mental health and the baby's growth and development.

Complaints felt by postpartum mothers can be prevented or handled with several efforts using both modern and traditional methods. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that health care during the postpartum period can be started 24 hours after giving birth or when the mother is in a physiological postpartum state. This treatment can be carried out by competent personnel such as doctors, midwives or nurses. This health care is an effort to improve the level of health as a mother in general and during the postpartum period and breastfeeding in particular. Being physically healthy and comfortable will have an effect on a mother's psychology. Mothers become happier and more confident in carrying out their role during the postpartum and breastfeeding period. Efforts that can be made to prevent or handle several complaints felt by mothers include massage for postpartum mothers, skin care using traditional ingredients, facial acupressure, beauty care, control according to the schedule determined by the birth attendant and consumption of nutritious food, adequate rest. .

The purpose of writing this scientific article is to determine the relationship between body care and health in postpartum mothers

LITERATURE REVIEW

The postpartum period begins with the birth of the placenta and the return of a woman's womb to its pre-pregnancy form. The postpartum period lasts 6 weeks or 42 days. During the postpartum period, the mother will experience many changes. Physical, mental, spiritual, social and economic changes will be experienced by mothers during this period. According to Yuliana and Hakim (2020), mothers will experience a lot of discomfort in the early postpartum period, which will turn into a pathological condition when they do not receive good care.

The postpartum period is divided into several stages, namely:

- a. Immediate postpartum is 0-24 hours after giving birth. This period is a critical phase where cases of postpartum hemorrhage often occur.
- b. Early postpartum is a period of more than 24 hours to 1 week. During this period, health workers really need their role in the mentoring process to monitor the mother's condition and early detection of postpartum disorders
- c. Late postpartum is a period that lasts more than 1 to 6 weeks. During this period, midwives are required to physically monitor mothers and provide counseling for the Family Planning program.
- d. Remote postpartum is the time needed for mothers to recover and be healthy, especially during pregnancy and childbirth.

Stages of adjustment to the mother's psychology in the post partum period, namely:

- a. Fase Taking in
- b. Fase Taking Hold
- c. Fase Letting Go

According to Ambarwati (2020), changes and discomfort experienced by mothers during the postpartum period include:

a. Breast

There is breast swelling for several days after giving birth. To relieve discomfort, apply warm and cold compresses to the breast area.

Rahim Kram pada Rahim. Konsultasikan pada dokter untuk terapi selanjutnya.

b. Perineum/Pain after giving birth

Perineal pain due to lacerations. Do Kegel exercises, compress the area with a cold compress wrapped in a towel or you can also sit on a pillow.

c. Leukorea

There is vaginal discharge for 2-4 weeks after giving birth. Immediately consult a doctor about these complaints.

d. Constipation

Occurs due to lack of fiber and water intake, hemorrhoids and physiological changes in the mother giving birth. Get enough fluids and fiber. Do Kegel exercises.

e. Frequent sweating

The body excretes excessive fluid due to the normal increase in intracellular fluid during pregnancy through this route and diuresis. Maintain personal skin hygiene, avoid using blankets and wear comfortable clothes.

e. Hair loss and skin changes

The decrease in hormones after giving birth means that hair will fall out easily in around 5 months. Using special shampoo for hair loss.

f. Breast enlargement

here is increased vascularization and congestion as well as a combination of accumulation and milk stasis

g. Hemorrhoids

If postpartum mothers experience hemorrhoids, they will feel pain for several days. Hemorrhoids can cause trauma and become more edematous during the second stage of labor

h. Stretch marks

During pregnancy it will widen as the fetus develops. It cannot disappear quickly and takes months to appear fainter. It can be lost by exfoliating, laser therapy, regularly applying natural ingredients such as olive oil and honey.

i. Melasma

Can be caused by sun exposure and side effects of family planning pills. This can be overcome by not being exposed to sunlight too often from 10-14 pm.

j. Pimple

Hormonal changes can affect oil production on facial skin. Excess oil can clog pores with dirt and dead skin cells. This problem can disappear by itself. To prevent this, wash your face diligently, to treat it, use cream or lotion that is relatively safe for mothers and babies.

k. Eczema

Hormonal changes in a postpartum mother's body can trigger eczema or dermatitis. Eczema usually appears on the surrounding area, face, eyes, back of the neck and genital area in the mother. Treatment that can be done is to apply

cream to the problem area. Other efforts include not scratching the skin, regularly compressing irritated skin and reducing the use of warm water when bathing.

l. Linea nigra

There is an increase in hormones that stimulate the appearance of melanocytes. This skin disorder is physiological and will disappear over time. However, if the mother feels disturbed, she can use a safe cream.

m. Telogen Effluvium

Hair loss that occurs suddenly after giving birth. Usually lasts 6 (six months). Consult a doctor if you feel it is very disturbing and can be treated independently by using shampoo to prevent hair loss. Or get hair treatment at the salon.

Traditional care can also be given to postpartum mothers, including consuming maternity herbal packages, betel leaf extract drinks, turmeric and ginger decoctions, pilis compresses, massages, body scrubs, consuming herbal minimans that are safe for breastfeeding mothers.

Both traditional and modern care are efforts that postpartum mothers can make to maintain health and beauty. According to Indryani (2022), the benefits of treatment for postpartum mothers are that the skin becomes beautiful and clean and the body becomes slim. This treatment can also be done in combination or modification.

From the literature above, mothers who undergo the postpartum period will still maintain their health and beauty by carrying out several measures that are guaranteed to be safe.

METHODOLOGY

The research method used is a quantitative method with a retrospective approach. This research was conducted in October-December 2023 in the working area of Turi District, Lamongan Regency, East Java Province, Indonesia. Data was collected through questionnaires filled out by respondents, then an interview process was carried out using an interview guide to assist the interview process. The sampling technique used is the total population. The research sample was 35 postpartum mothers who were studied on the first day postpartum (day 43 after giving birth). The independent variables studied were body care during the postpartum period, the dependent variable was health conditions during the postpartum period.

RESULTS

Geographically, Lamongan Regency is located at 6°51'54" - 7°23'06" South Latitude and 112°33'45" - 112°33'45" East Longitude. Lamongan Regency has an area of approximately 1,812.8 km² or + 3.78% of the area of East Java Province. Lamongan Regency consists of 27 sub-districts with details of 462 villages and 12 sub-districts. To the west, it borders Bojonegoro and Tuban Regencies, to the north it borders the Java Sea, to the east it borders Gresik Regency, to the south it borders Mojokerto and Jombang Regencies. Turi District is one of the Districts located on the main road of Lamongan Regency. Based on the results of the research carried out, the following results were obtained:

A. General Data

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents based on age in Kec. Turi, Kab. Lamongan

No	Age	Amount	%
1	17-25 years old	5	14,3
2	26-35 years old	12	34,3
3	36-45 years old	13	37,1
4	46-55 years old	5	14,3
Total		35	100

From table 1, it can be seen from the research results that the age of postpartum mothers in the Turi sub-district working area is almost half of the respondents aged 36-45 years, namely 13 people (37.1%).

Table 2. Characteristics of respondents based on education level in Kec. Turi, Kab. Lamongan

No	Age	Amount	%
1	Didn't go to school/didn't graduate	0	0
2	SD	0	0
3	SMP	8	22,8
4	SMA	20	57,1
5	PT	7	20
Total		35	100

From table 2, it can be seen from the research results that the educational level of postpartum mothers was mostly high school education, namely 20 people (57.1%).

Table 3. Characteristics of respondents based on parity in Kec. Turi, Kab. Lamongan

No	Age	Amount	%
1	Primipara	18	51,4
2	Multipara	12	34,3
3	Grandemultipara	5	14,3
Total		35	100

From table 3, it can be seen from the research results that the characteristics of respondents based on parity, the majority of postpartum mothers are primigravida, namely 18 people (51.4%).

B. Special Data

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Body Care During the Postpartum Period by Mothers During the Postpartum Period in Kec. Turi, Kab. Lamongan

No	Age	Amount	%
1	Performing Maintenance		
	a. Tradisional	23	66
	b. Modern	5	14
	Total Maintenance	28	80
2	Didn't Performing Maintenance		20
	Total didn't Maintenance	7	20
	Total	35	100

From table 4, it can be seen from the research results that almost all postpartum mothers carried out postpartum care using both traditional and modern methods, namely 28 people (80%). There are very few postpartum mothers who do not carry out postpartum care, namely 7 people (20%).

Table 5. Frequency Distribution of Types of Body Care During the Postpartum Period by Mothers During the Postpartum Period in Kec. Turi, Kab. Lamongan

No	Types of Treatment	Amount	%
1	Tradisional		
	a. Consume a maternity herbal package	2	7,14
	b. Drink betel leaf extract	2	7,14
	c. Drink ginger turmeric decoction	2	7,14
	d. Compress pills	3	10,71
	e. Massage	7	25
	f. Using stagen or octopus	2	7,14
	g. Use tapel concoction	2	7,14
	f. Herbal scrub	3	10,71
2	Modern		
	a.Using cream for stretch marks	2	7,14
	b. Spot laser	2	7,14
	c. Factory produced scrub	1	3,57
	Total	28	100

From table 6, it can be seen from the research results that most of the postpartum mothers were in healthy condition, namely 24 people (65.71%).

Table 7. Cross Tabulation of Types of Body Care by Postpartum Mothers in Kec. Turi, Kab. Lamongan

Body care	Postpartum Mother's Health						Amount	%
	healthy	%	Quite Healty	%	Not healthy	%		
do	23	65,7	4	11,4	1	2,85	28	79,9
Don't	1	2,85	1	2,85	5	14,28	7	19,9
	Total							100

From table 7, it can be seen from the research results that there is a tendency for postpartum mothers who undergo postpartum care to undergo the postpartum period in a healthy condition, namely 23 people (65.7%), while those who do not undergo treatment are more likely to experience unhealthy conditions, namely 5 people. (14.28%).

DISCUSSION

From table 4, the research results show that almost all postpartum mothers carry out postpartum care using both traditional and modern methods, namely 28 people (80%). There are very few postpartum mothers who do not carry out postpartum care, namely 7 people (20%). According to Pattianasary (2020), postpartum mothers need postpartum care. In postpartum care using traditional methods, almost all postpartum mothers do it, namely 28 people (80%). According to research results from Sembiring & Sismudjito (2015), people's daily habits and experiences in solving health problems are influenced by local culture. Beliefs about culture also influence health services for postpartum mothers in that place (Rahayu, 2017). From this, it can be concluded that people tend to be more confident that traditional treatment methods are more capable of preventing disease or treating the health problems they face. Of the traditional care methods, postpartum mothers tend to prefer massage as postpartum care. Based on the results of additional interviews, postpartum mothers who chose massage said that massage provided a feeling of comfort and relaxation for bodies that were tired during the pregnancy process and undergoing the postpartum period with various new tasks. Mother feels more relaxed and regains her energy after getting a massage. In an article in the Health Technology Assessment Section-MaHTAS (2018) it is stated that massage can increase serotonin and dopamine, reduce cortisol and norepinephrine. Increased serotonin can reduce back and leg pain. Furthermore, an increase in dopamine accompanied by a decrease in cortisol and norepinephrine is also able to support the mother's sleep activity and can reduce the mother's psychological problems. Several changes that occur to the mother after giving birth, the journey of pregnancy for 9 months certainly makes the mother's physical and psychological condition change. So body care through massage to restore the condition of the mother's body from feeling tired is an option that can be considered. Massage procedures are of course tailored to the needs of postpartum mothers, carried out by experts and not carried out in dangerous areas. From the research results, most postpartum mothers are primiparous mothers, where psychologically a primiparous mother is experiencing her role as a mother for the first time. So some adaptations will be made quickly. This process certainly drains mothers' energy, so they prefer relaxation methods to relax tense muscles. There were very few mothers who chose postpartum care using modern methods, namely 7 people (20%). From the results of additional interviews, according to them, modern care will economically increase their expenses, they have to leave the house and leave the baby to get treatment at the salon, there are several postpartum mothers who are worried that using cream will affect the quality of the milk and thus harm the baby's health. They prefer natural ingredients to be used in treatments.

Based on table 6, the majority of postpartum mothers are in good health during the postpartum period. Healthy is what is meant here, namely that for 42 days the postpartum mother has never experienced pain or complaints that interfere with her activities. While quite healthy, the mother experienced complaints but did not go to bed rest. For the sick category, postpartum mothers

experience complaints of pain and bed rest for several days. These complaints include fever, swollen breasts, stress, dizziness, lack of appetite until weakness, body aches, dull and not bright skin. Postpartum mothers should not experience an increase in temperature to more than 38°C. Postpartum mothers who show abnormal symptoms are immediately referred to a health facility for early treatment (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2013). Apart from clinical and psychological conditions, there are several things that must be considered, namely personal hygiene, adequate rest, abdominal muscle exercises or postpartum exercises and breast care (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2013). Research conducted by Usman and Sapril (2018) stated that traditional care in the family is one way to maintain the health of postpartum mothers.

Based on table 7, the tendency for postpartum mothers who undergo postpartum care will undergo postpartum period in a healthy condition, namely 23 people (65.7%), while those who do not undergo treatment are more likely to experience an unhealthy condition, namely 5 people (14.28%). According to Arnanda (2021), body care has a positive impact such as relaxing or warming the body, improving the mother's blood circulation after giving birth. Mothers who diligently care for the postpartum period will have an impact on their health conditions during the postpartum period. The mother's body will return to its prime, the mother's self-confidence will return so that the mother will be able to carry out postpartum activities smoothly. By carrying out postpartum care, mothers also have "me time" so that physical and psychological discomfort is easy for mothers to recognize because they can focus on themselves. This treatment will of course work if it has support from the family. According to Tulas, et al (2017) postpartum mothers really need to maintain their condition because they are in the recovery period and are vulnerable to experiencing health problems. During this recovery period, the mother will generally feel uncomfortable. Besides that, the role as a parent also begins. Mother will focus on taking care of her baby. This will more or less drain the mother's energy. So if during this period the mother is not in prime physical condition, the mother will be very vulnerable to experiencing baby blues, physical pain and can become depressed.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Postpartum mothers in the working area of the Turi Health Center, Lamongan Regency, mostly choose postpartum care using traditional methods. Mothers who receive treatment during the postpartum period tend to have a healthy body condition during the postpartum period. Mothers really need care during the postpartum period to obtain a strong physical and healthy mentality.

FURTHER STUDY

Postpartum mothers in the working area of the Turi Health Center, Lamongan Regency, mostly choose postpartum care using traditional methods. Mothers who receive treatment during the postpartum period tend to have a healthy body condition during the postpartum period. Mothers really need care during the postpartum period to obtain a strong physical and healthy mentality.

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